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Review Article

Development Of Scientific Marketing in Twentieth Century in Ayurveda System

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ABSTRACT

This review tracks changes to a globally recognized and proven medical system in consideration of the evolution of the scientific marketing of Ayurveda in the 20th century. Modern technologies such as AI expanded the news of Ayurveda and demanded changes in the fields of philosophy, research and regulations. The article examines historical challenges in implementing Ayurveda and highlights the importance of technical validation for global acceptance. By focusing on digital marketing and social media strategies, it aims to position Ayurveda as a mainstream healthcare option and promote its continued growth.

INTRODUCTION

This article describes the possibility of activating Ayurveda and integrating it into a global healthcare system. He emphasizes the need for technical results to support the main global management, taking into account both historical failures and current issues. The objective is to improve the implementation of Ayurveda, positioning it as a scientifically validated and worldwide medicine system.[1] Ayurveda, an ancient and scientifically based health system, is undergoing a paradigm shift in various areas including its philosophy, research, development,

regulatory framework and administrative structures. The integration of modern technologies including artificial intelligence is expanding its global reach. In order to fully understand the possibility, it is essential to revisit the evolution of fairy postcolonialism, which has established the basics of modernization and industrialization in the modern world.[2] The British colonial period significantly weakened the traditional medical system in India, diminishing the importance of Ayush Veda and its role in the international arena. In order to advance global recognition of Ayush Veda in the

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contemporary context, it is essential to evaluate its fundamental aspects such as its role in India, its recognition as a complementary or primary medical system, and its philosophy and ethics as an indigenous practice. Key considerations include Āyurveda credibility, sustainability, global marketing strategies, research transparency, and scientific validation. Efforts to revitalize Āyurveda began in the late 19th century, aiming to modernize its terminology and literature to enhance global adaptability and acceptance.[3]The World Health Organization's inclusion of AYUSH terminology in the 11th edition of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) marks an important step towards globalizing Ayurveda, allowing for better research, evaluation and comparison of traditional medicines.Despite the economic potential of traditional health systems, they have been largely ignored due to industrialization-led development.However, growing awareness of organic products is enabling the herbal industry to play a significant and sustainable role in the global economy.[4]Currently, India, the world's leading economy by purchasing power parity, has formally recognised Ayurveda and other traditional systems of medicine under AYUSH, which play a vital role in public health through comprehensive, evidence-based practices.Support from autonomous bodies, research collaborations, policy, IT integration and specialised consultancies has expanded the scope and structure of AYUSH registered educational institutions, hospitals and professionals.[5]The Indian medicinal plant industry, although lucrative, faces significant challenges in the areas of quality control, processing, infrastructure, pharmacovigilance, clinical trials, biopiracy and ethical issues. If left unresolved, these issues could

hinder the economic and scientific progress of Ayurveda. The article provides a meta-analysis of the opportunities and obstacles to the globalization of Āyurveda, focusing on its epistemology, educational system, herbal marketing, and research and development.[6]

2] History Of Ayurveda:-

Ayurveda originated in the 2nd Century BC, with foundational principles from the Hindu philosophical schools of Vaisheshika and Nyaya, and the manifestation framework Samkhya.The Vaisheshika school emphasized observing inferences and perceptions about a patient's pathology for effective treatment, while the Nyaya school advocated for comprehensive knowledge of the patient and disease.Vaisesika also classifies the attributes of things into six types namely, Dravya (matter), Vishesh (particularity), Karma (activity), Samanya (community), Samavaya (essence) and Guna (quality).[7,8]The Vaisheshika and Nyaya schools later merged to form the Nyaya-Vaisheshika school, which played a key role in promoting and disseminating Ayurvedic knowledge. Ayurveda is traditionally believed to have divine origins with the Hindu god Brahma, the creator of the universe. [9,10]Ayurveda's knowledge of healing is believed to have been passed down from the creator god Brahma to sages who shared it with their students and the public through scriptures and oral tradition. The medicinal properties of herbs were documented as poetic "Shlokas." The Hindu healing system is rooted in the four Vedas — Yajur, Rig, Sam, and Atharva with the Rig Veda describing 67 herbs and 1,028 Shlokas, and the Atharva Veda and Yajur Veda describing 293 and 81 herbs, respectively.The Ayurvedic knowledge of the Rig Veda and Atharva Veda is attributed to the sage Atreya, who is said to have received it

from Lord Indra, who in turn received it from Lord Brahma.[11,12] The Agnivesha collected Vedic knowledge and was later compiled by Charaka and other scholars as the Charaka Samhita, covering all aspects of Ayurvedic medicine. The Sushruta Samhita focuses on the science of surgery.[13-16] The "Charaka Samhita" and the "Sushruta Samhita" are still used today by traditional healers and have been translated into several languages, including Tibetan, Greek, Chinese, Arabic and Persian.[17] Besides the Charaka Samhita, there are other notable Ayurvedic texts such as the Nigantu Grantha, Madhava Nidhana and Bhava Prakasha, but the Charaka Samhita remains the most revered.[18,19]

3] Implementation Of Ayurveda: -

Indians have a strong passion for medicinal plants, using them for various health applications, from treating colds to enhancing memory and immunity. The Indian System of Medicine (ISM) includes both indigenous systems and those adopted over time.[20] About 25,000 effective herbal recipes are used in traditional medicine in rural communities of India.[21] India has over 1.5 million traditional medicine practitioners and more than 7,000 medicinal drug manufacturing units.[22] Practitioners of traditional Indian medicine collectively consume about 2,000 tons of herbs annually, with a focus on natural products. Ayurveda stands out for its accessibility, affordability, low cost, and growing economic importance.[23] Ayurveda has extensive infrastructure, including educational institutions, research centers, registered practitioners, hospitals, pharmacies and manufacturing units supported by government initiatives to promote its development.

3.1 Administrative bodies for development of traditional medicine

The Department of AYUSH, established in 2003, aims to regulate, standardize and promote traditional medicine in India through policies, quality control and educational advancements. The Department of AYUSH comprises five Central Research Councils, two regulatory bodies, two laboratories, eleven educational institutes and a drug manufacturing unit. It focuses on regulating and promoting AYUSH systems through improved education, research initiatives and cultivation of medicinal plants. The department aims to ensure quality control and standardization of traditional medicine, with the support of the Drug Control Cell, which oversees compliance with the Drugs and Cosmetics Act.[24] The Drug Control Cell supervises the activities of the Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani Drugs Technical Advisory Board (ASUDTAB) and the Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani Drugs Advisory Committee (ASUDCC), which advises on technical matters relating to herbal medicines. In addition, the National Medicinal Plant Board (NMPB) is responsible for conservation, cultivation, supply and demand, research, trade and quality control of medicinal plants.[25] Several initiatives and committees have been established for some time to promote traditional medicine.

3.2 Education and practices for expansion of Ayurveda

In ancient India the education system and traditional knowledge were very well organized. Taxila was built from 700 BC to 300 AD and was seen as a prestigious center for higher learning.

Table 1

Pre- and Post-independent initiatives on Indian system of medicine [ISM].

Pre-Independence Initiatives

1920: The Indian National Congress advocated for the recognition of traditional medicine.

1943: The Bhore Committee recognized the contributions of indigenous medicine but did not recommend its further development.

1946: The Chopra Committee sought to harmonize indigenous medicine with Western practices.

Post-Independence Initiatives:

1947: A health policy was established with a committee headed by Colonel Solhey.

1955: The Dave Committee established uniform standards for Ayurvedic education.

1956: Indian Medical Council Act (IMC Act) established.

1956: Setup of Pgtri at the University of Gujarat Ayurveda.

1964: Change of drug and cosmetic law, 1940.

1970: Central Council or Indian Medicine Act Regulation Medicine Systems.

1989: National Academy of Ayurveda founded.

1995: Establishment of a separate department for Indian Systems of Medicine and Homeopathy.

1998: Inclusion of 32 Pharmacopoeia Standardization Laboratories.

1999: Initiation of IEC programs to promote Ayurveda through non-governmental organizations.

2006: Mandatory heavy metal testing for exports.

2008: Introduction of Pharmacovigilance Guidelines for Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani medicines

2009: Establishment of International Cooperation Council for Indian Systems of Medicine and Homeopathy [26] Nalanda, located near Patna (Bihar), was a prominent Buddhist monastery and educational centre in the 6th and 7th centuries AD and housed numerous manuscripts on philosophy, religion, grammar, logic, literature, Vedas, Vedanta, Sankhya philosophy, Dharmasastras, Puranas, astronomy, astrology and medicine.[27]Until the 18th century, Indian

medicine was based on the Ayurveda and Unani systems. During British rule, the East India Company and Christian missionaries established several educational institutions, including the Banaras Sanskrit College in 1792 to promote traditional knowledge, and the Hindu College (now Presidency College) and Raven Shaw College, both founded in 1816 to promote Indian education.[28]In the early 19th century, British rulers began training some Indians in allopathic medicine, and the first formal medical training program, the Native Doctor Course, was established in 1824 at the Calcutta Sanskrit College. In 1835, the Calcutta Medical College became the first medical college in Asia to be established on the initiative of the British.[29]After independence, several important institutions were established in India to improve the education and practice of Ayurveda. 1956: Institute of Postgraduate Training and Research in Ayurveda (IPTRA) was established in Jamnagar, Gujarat. 1963: Banaras Hindu University started postgraduate training in Indian medicine and later became the Institute of Medical Sciences. 1976: Ayurveda National Institute (NIA) was established in Jaipur to improve Ayurveda's educational standards. 1988: The formation of a leading religion started by the Ayusha Bureau through the New Delhi Ayurveda National Academy. 2003: The All India Institute of Ayurveda (AIIA) is established in New Delhi to set standards for postgraduate and doctoral training in the field of Ayurveda. The Ministry of AYUSH oversees 86 educational institutions, including 11 national research institutes, and the Central Council of Indian Medicine (CCIM) regulates standards of education and practice in the Ayurvedic, Siddha and Unani systems.[30]

3.3 Ayurvedic pharmacopoeia of India and drug testing laboratories

In India, the Pharmaceutical Board of India (PLIM) which oversees pharmacy standards and quality control of Ayurvedic, Unani and Siddha (ASU) medicines under the Drugs and Cosmetics Act was established in 1970. They have published a monograph in the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API), which comprises of 7 volumes of Single Drug Monographs (Part I) and 3 volumes of Compound Formulations (Part II). Part I contains 540 monographs, including 418 in the first five volumes (1990-2006), 101 in Volume 6 (2008), and 21 in Volume 7. It is. Part II includes 101 monographs released between 2007 and 2010. The Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI), created to standardize formulations, has two parts: Part I (1978, 144 formulations) and Part II (2000, 191 formulations). Various councils and research institutes contribute to the safety and quality standards of polyherbal and herbo-mineral preparations. Moreover, Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) 2007 details the specifications of 58 herbs, their identity, description, quality control and reference standards. [31]

3.4 Regulatory assessment and legislature

The Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940 and Drugs and Cosmetics Rules, 1945 regulate the import, manufacture, distribution and sale of drugs and cosmetics in India. Initially, Ayurvedic medicine was excluded from this act. However, in 1964, the Drugs and Cosmetics (Amendment) Act introduced a definition of Ayurvedic drugs and regulatory provisions for their control, effective from September 15, 1964, under Chapter IV-A. [32] The Drugs and Cosmetics Act lists in its first schedule 54 authoritative Ayurvedic texts. In 1982, an amendment introduced the definition of Ayurvedic proprietary medicine in section 3(h). Her recognition of the need for excellent manufacturing practices (GMP) in the Indian Medical System (ISM), the rules of drugs and cosmetics were revised in 2000

to demand the ISM drug manufacturer. Furthermore, the rules of the 7th amendment to 2001 have established the requirements for approval for the ASU screening test, and the GMP compliance is obliged to all ISM manufacturing units and guarantee quality standards. [33] The guidelines outline key strategies for the production and evaluation of herbal medicines, with emphasis on standards of quality and efficacy. The Drugs and Magic Cures Act 1954 prohibits the advertising and import and export of certain drugs and cures, specifically targeting those that falsely claim to treat certain illnesses or that mislead the public. [34]

3.5 Traditional knowledge digital library (TKDL): knowledge substantiation

Traditional Knowledge Digital Library (TKDL) is a unique database developed by CSIR and the AYUSH department. Around 212,000 medicinal properties of Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha are documented in patent-compatible format and are available in five major international languages. The database is protected by national and international intellectual property laws. [35] TKDL offers easy access to traditional medical knowledge for patent experts, overcome linguistic barriers and reformat the content in a structure compatible with patents. Using the traditional classification system (TKRC), it translates local knowledge of languages such as Sanskrit, Ourdou and Tamil in globally affordable formats [36] in 2003, the WIPO Intergovernmental Committee established international standards for traditional knowledge databases. In 2009, the TKDL signed an access agreement with the European Patent Office (EPO) to improve the quality of patent examination based on traditional knowledge. This cooperation has

been acknowledged by the Director General of WIPO.[37]

4] Ethical Consideration In Ayurveda

4.1]Regulatory Legislations

Allopathy, AYUSH, and homeopathy are regulated by separate statutes with separate registrations, reflecting the legislature's intention to maintain the independence of these systems. Under the Indian Medical Central Council Act, 1970, AYUSH practitioners are identified as "vaidas" and "hakims" rather than "physicians". Although they can use the latest diagnostic tools in their practice, the Supreme Court has ruled that AYUSH practitioners cannot practice allopathic medicine unless they are registered under the Indian Medical Council Act, 1956. The Supreme Court made it clear that the Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1945, regulates the control of drugs but does not regulate the right to practise medicine. The Indian Medical Council Act, 1956 generally prohibits AYUSH doctors from practising allopathic medicines, although some states allow AYUSH doctors to prescribe allopathic medicines during periods of doctor shortage. The practice varies according to state laws, and the Indian Medical Association has legally challenged such permission in Maharashtra. The Supreme Court has allowed Ayurvedic, Siddha, Unani and Homeopathic practitioners to prescribe allopathic medicines only if the state government allows it. The Ministry of Health and Family Welfare has asked states to create a separate register for such practitioners to ensure cross-practice. In one famous case, an Ayurvedic doctor was found liable for negligence after misdiagnosing a serious reaction to an allopathic drug, highlighting that state approval does not absolve doctors from liability for interrelated errors.

Courts have emphasised the liability of doctors in medical negligence cases across the system.

4.2] Decisions Of The Supreme Court

In *Dr. Laxman Balakrishna Joshi v. Dr. Trambak Babu Godbole*, the Supreme Court laid down the liability of a doctor as follows: (i) care in deciding to take on a case, (ii) care in selecting the treatment, (iii) care in carrying out the treatment. The violation of these obligations constitutes negligence. Practicing medicine outside a trained system with unqualified is fake. Liability for negligence can arise when the necessary skills are not present or when skills are used improperly. In one case where a homeopath prescribed a dangerous treatment for Guinea worm infection, causing the patient's death, the court found this to be negligent and reckless. The Supreme Court, after considering the Bombay Homoeopathic Practitioners Act, 1959 and the Indian Medical Council Act, 1956, reiterated that practitioners registered in one system of medicine (e.g., homeopathy) can practice only within that system, while practicing in another system (e.g., allopathy) is considered unqualified and punishable. The Court defined such unauthorised practice as quackery, where negligence is presumed without further proof. Exceptions are only possible if cross-practice is permitted by the state after additional training, in which case the specialist must demonstrate special competence and may require ongoing training to ensure public safety. In *Bhanwar Kanwar v. Gupta*, the Supreme Court dealt with an Ayurvedic doctor who claimed complete cure for epileptic seizures but prescribed allopathic medicines under the guise of Ayurvedic treatment. Although the doctor was licensed to practice allopathy in Uttar Pradesh, the court found him guilty of unfair trade practices for misleading

the patient's family. The court ruled that to ensure patient safety and respect informed consent, cross-system doctors must transparently inform patients when prescribing treatment outside the approved system.

4.3] Ethical Guidelines

The Medical Council of India (MCI) Rules strictly prohibit any person without a recognised qualification and registration with the MCI from practicing modern medicine. According to para 1.1.3, only those who are qualified in the field of modern medicine can practice it; practitioners of other systems are prohibited from practicing it in any form. Article 6.5 further prohibits allopathic physicians from prescribing or promoting alternative or complementary medicines whose composition or origin is unknown. However, the Indian Code of Ethics for Traditional Medicine has no such provision to prevent cross practice and protect the integrity of each profession. Additionally, the Supreme Court has ruled that foreign medical graduates (MBBS holders from countries like the USSR, China, and Nepal) must pass a screening test for registration in India. The Court underscored that without proper qualifications and MCI-prescribed certification, individuals cannot be involved in public healthcare, stressing that the same standards should apply to practitioners of alternative systems who wish to practice modern medicine.[38]

5] strategies of ayurveda system

5.1] Measures to prevent infectious condition as described in Ayurvedic classics

Ayurveda prescribes a diet and behavioral regime (Charya) to help an individual adapt to seasonal changes while maintaining a balance in the body. Its main objective Swasthyasya

Swasthya Rakshanam focuses on maintaining good health and not just curing diseases. Ayurveda focuses

on preventing disease progression and boosting immunity, which are essential approaches in managing infectious diseases like COVID-19. Daily practices such as Nasya (nasal drops) and Kavala Gundusha (gargling) promote nasal and oral hygiene and may prevent gateways of infection. The Ayurvedic concept that the nose is the gateway to the body (Naso hi shirasi dwaram) is consistent with modern thinking on mucosal immunity. By strengthening these barriers to entry, Ayurvedic measures can act as a "physiological mask" to reduce the risk of viral entry and transmission.

A] Din Acharya

Ayurveda's Dinacharya (daily regimen) is a structured lifestyle that aligns the body's biological clock with nature's circadian rhythms, helping to balance bodily moods and promote well-being. This regimen includes specific practices like waking up early (Brahmi muhurta), drinking water stored in copper or silver pots (Ushapana), and practicing oral hygiene like brushing and gargling (Kavala Gandusha). Every step, including cutting nails, bathing, wearing shoes and protecting yourself from the sun, is aimed at promoting health, improving digestion, increasing discipline and increasing longevity. Ayurveda also recommends storing drinking water in copper vessels because of its antibacterial properties, effective against harmful bacteria such as *Vibrio cholerae*, *Shigella flexneri*, *E. Coli* and *salmonella*. Research confirms the ability to destroy the bacterial film, and provides a potential solution for water purification, which is restricted in access to water.

B] Rutucharya

In line with its preventive focus, Ayurveda prescribes seasonal regimens (Ritucharya) to maintain health and prevent diseases by adjusting

diet and lifestyle according to the change in seasons. Human health depends on changes in the environment as the body synchronizes with the rhythm of the external environment. If your body is unable to adapt to seasonal stressors, it can lead to illness, weakened immunity, and increased susceptibility to disease.

C] Personal hygiene

Indian traditions emphasize the importance of hygienic practices such as washing hands and feet upon entering a home and before eating, wearing clean clothes after bathing, and avoiding sharing towels or wet clothes all of which are described in the Sushruta Samhita. Certain practices such as changing clothes between activities and sleep, bathing after a funeral, and drinking without touching the lips to the container emphasize early prevention of infection. Although they were once thought to be superstition, it is recognized that these traditions are now valuable to maintain hygiene and prevent illness.

D] Environmental hygiene

Ayurveda emphasizes the importance of environmental hygiene (Jala, Vayu, Bhumi, Kala) for human health by linking external environmental factors like water, air and soil for the prevention of diseases. Research has demonstrated that Ayurvedic medicinal smoke removes various pathogenic bacteria from the air and has bactericidal properties. Traditional methods of purifying water, air, and soil, although basic, have scientific validity and could be effectively promoted for more widespread use, especially in rural and urban areas.

E] Role of diet

Indian culture has long recognized the important role of food in health, using diet as a preventative and therapeutic tool. Rooted in traditional medical systems, Indian traditional foods aim to support physical and mental well-

being. Global understanding of the role of diet in preventing disease only really took off in the 20th century, but ancient India stressed the importance of diet much earlier. A good example is rasam, a South Indian soup that contains medicinal ingredients like tamarind, turmeric, pepper and garlic. Traditionally used to treat symptoms like fever, cold and digestive disorders, rasam is still a functional food that is regularly consumed for its health benefits. In India, many spices in everyday use, such as turmeric, garlic, and ginger, have significant antiviral properties and can be therapeutic when consumed regularly. In Ayurveda, they are included in both food and medicines for their antibacterial properties. Turmeric, containing curcumin, is widely consumed and has shown antiviral activity against influenza, Zika, and chikungunya by interfering with viral binding. Garlic, with its active compound allicin, and ginger, revered in Ayurveda as universal medicine, both exhibit antiviral actions by inhibiting viral replication and attachment. These foods underscore the therapeutic potential of traditional dietary practices in supporting immune health. Onions and garlic are potent antiviral foods rich in organosulfur compounds like quercetin and allicin, which help inhibit viral infections. These compounds can block virus attachment to host cells, disrupt viral genome processes, and prevent viral assembly. Quercetin prevents viral entry and replication, and allicin penetrates cell membranes to prevent viral proliferation. These properties make onion and garlic valuable for supporting immunity through the diet.

F] Importance of hot water

Ayurveda emphasizes the medicinal benefits of hot water, particularly for digestion, throat pain relief, and clearing phlegm. During COVID-19, the Ministry of AYUSH recommended hot water and teas with pepper, ginger, and Tulsi for immune

support. Ayurveda views hot water as beneficial for digesting Ama, a proinflammatory byproduct associated with higher infection risk. Traditionally, warm water with spices is consumed across India to aid in conditions like fever, inflammation, and respiratory allergies.

G] Concept of immunity and immunomodulation

Ayurveda likens a healthy body to barren land, where infections cannot thrive. Immunity in Ayurveda is categorized as Sahajabala (natural), Kalajabala (seasonal or age-related), and Yuktikrutabala (enhanced through lifestyle, diet, and rasayanas). Instead of directly targeting pathogens, Ayurveda focuses on strengthening natural immunity through daily (Dinacharya) and seasonal (Rutucharya) regimens, cleansing practices such as Panchakarma and immune modulators. Treatment is personalized according to the Dosha Prakriti types - Vata, Pitta and Kapha - to optimize immune resilience.

H] Potential immunomodulators mentioned in Ayurveda

In Ayurveda, a weakened immune system allows viruses and bacteria to thrive in the body. Popular health boosters like Balya (tonics) and Rasayana (immunomodulators) boost immunity, fight illnesses and promote faster recovery. Ashwagandha and Guduchi are important Ayurvedic herbs that boost immunity and studies have shown the effectiveness of

Ashwagandha in preventing and treating COVID-19. Ashwagandha may act as an antiviral, anti-inflammatory and immune restorative agent, showing potential in treating COVID-19 symptoms and inflammatory conditions. The father of the research is recommended for Lasayana herbs such as Ashva Ganda, Gudochi, Amalaki, and Yashitimadu to confirm clinical effects. [39]

6] Artificial Inteligeant Used Ayurveda System

AI is transforming daily life by boosting efficiency, safety, and convenience, especially in healthcare, education, and smart cities. In medicine, AI enhances diagnostic imaging, enables personalized treatment, and uses predictive analytics to anticipate disease outbreaks, significantly improving healthcare management.

Personalized Treatment data

Collection And Integration

AI algorithms can integrate complex patient data (medical history, lifestyle habits, and genetic information) to create a holistic health profile, which enables the development of personalized Ayurvedic treatment strategies by identifying individual vulnerabilities and health trends.

Analysis Of Data and Identification of Patterns

AI will use advanced data analytics to identify connections within integrated datasets, supporting Ayurveda's focus on genetic influences on lifestyle and health. Predictive analytics will enable AI to predict health issues and provide precise, proactive Ayurvedic interventions tailored to the individual.

Personalized Dosha Assessment

AI can convert Dosha's evaluation, provide accurate understanding, and accurately identify human dominant Dosha. In accordance with the current data, dynamic treatment adjustments are recommended based on dosha vibration from factors such as season, age, and lifestyle, and it is possible to secure adjustments with the principles of Ayurveda.

Customized Treatment Plans

By analyzing personal health data like medical history, lifestyle, genetics, etc., AI can recommend personalized Ayurvedic herbal prescriptions and dietary plans. This approach tailor's treatment to balance doshas and harmonize with prakriti,

providing precise and effective Ayurvedic interventions that improve overall health.

Feedback And Iterative Improvement

The AI system tracks a patient's progress in real time, using continuous feedback and monitoring via wearable devices, apps and interactions. This iterative learning process allows the AI to update its recommendations, ensuring Ayurvedic treatments remain adaptive and effective to meet changing medical needs.

Integration With Modern Medicine

AI can integrate Ayurvedic therapies with modern medicine to create comprehensive treatment plans that cover all aspects of a patient's health.

This multidisciplinary approach improves the individualization and effectiveness of care, providing a balanced, holistic treatment strategy.

Practical Implementation

AI algorithms improve the processing of Ayurveda by providing personalized database recommendations while guarantee confidentiality and security. Collaboration between an expert and a friendly interface guarantees the coordination of conventional knowledge and legal compliance.

Helping In Diagnosis

AI-based solutions enhance Ayurvedic diagnosis by providing data-driven insights into dosha imbalances through analysis of symptoms, physical characteristics, and mental states. By identifying symptom patterns such as digestive issues and fatigue, AI helps practitioners assess constitutional types and mental disorders, providing personalized treatment, and enhancing the dynamic approach to Ayurvedic healthcare.

Research And Development

Analyzing Large Datasets From Clinical Trials

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Mining Historical Texts For Traditional Remedies

Natural language processing (NLP) AI can mine historical Ayurvedic literature by scanning and analyzing ancient manuscripts to extract details about herbal blends, dosages, and preparation methods. By linking this data to modern research, AI can assess the effectiveness of traditional treatments and find new applications, bridging the gap between Ayurveda and modern science.

Accelerating The Research Process

AI accelerates Ayurvedic research by rapidly processing complex data, generating hypotheses and designing assays, reducing the time required to achieve actionable results. This helps validate traditional treatments, identify new drug substances, identify research gaps and predict outcomes, thereby modernizing Ayurveda and making it adaptable to modern medical needs.

Ai-Based Educational Platforms

In the future, AI-based educational systems will change the training of new Ayurvedic practitioners by enabling highly interactive and individualised learning experiences. These platforms will be capable of curating bespoke curriculums that adapt to each learner's pace, interests, and knowledge gaps, much like modern artificial intelligence-driven platforms such as Coursera and Khan Academy do videos, or practical exercises based on the student's development and performance. This customised approach guarantees that every student receives a comprehensive and engaging education, boosting their comprehension of specific Ayurvedic concepts and practices.[40]

7] Social media incline to trust in products of ayurveda:

This study aims to explore how millennials' environmental concerns relate to their social media use and consumption habits, and how digital platforms affect sustainability among this generation (Bedard & Tolmie, 2018). [41] The richness of the media and the reliability of the content are important factors in interaction with social networks. Rich media enhances larger parts, but content reliability affects consumer behaviour,

but hardly affects the creator. The influence of these factors on the relationship between intention and behaviour varies (Cao et al., 2021). [42] A systematic literature review of journals published between 2012 and 2023 was conducted using Google Scholar keywords such as "Generation Y Blog Users", "Patanjali Products", "Social Media Influence", "Perception of Organic Food", "Organic Food", "The Role of Trust", "Impact of Social Media", "Social Media Influence" and "User Engagement on Social Media Platforms".

Table 1: shows how social media leading to inclination of trust in products:

Sr.no	Contribution	Author
1	Digital media and printing marketing have a minimum effect on the behaviour of buyers of Ayurvedic products. Despite visibility, these platforms have not effectively affected solutions. This indicates that alternative marketing strategies are effective in recovering interest and participation in this market.	Bhilare, et al. (2021). [43]
2	Key elements of building a trustworthy blog include easy navigation, relevant content, an appealing aesthetic, and a good reputation. These elements encourage readers to return, share, and recommend your blog, contributing to its success and growth.	Pednekar & Mayekar(2021) [44]
3	Studies highlight the effectiveness of social media as a communication tool that promotes improved interpersonal interactions, improves customer access to services, boosts sales and supports brand marketing. Its benefits in terms of information sharing between different departments of the company make it a valuable tool for organizations that want to connect with their target audiences, strengthen their market presence and improve their internal communication.	Tashtoush, (2021). [45]
4	Social media acts as a powerful tool for organizations, enabling communication beyond face-to-face interactions. The benefits include better access to customers, increased sales, effective brand marketing, efficient communication between departments, and more. These benefits make social media essential for engaging with your target market, expanding your market presence, and improving internal communications.	Tashtoush, (2021). [46]
5	Media impact, the importance of information, and the allure of advertising are important elements affecting respondents' opinions of organic products. Out of all of these, "Information on usage, Internet, and Create awareness of the brand" had the biggest influence on consumer purchasing decisions. This emphasizes how crucial public education and awareness campaigns via media and digital platforms are in influencing consumers' decisions to buy organic products.	Balasubramanian & Rani (2020). [47]

6	The study emphasizes how important media exposure—including social media is in influencing customer opinions, especially for Vietnamese consumers. Good media coverage has a big impact on how they view and interact with food-related issues. This emphasizes how crucial it is to use the media to spread knowledge about food, safety, and health in Vietnam.	Pham,et al. (2019). [48]
7	The use of social media significantly influences the development of environmentally conscious behavior and sustainable purchase choices. This effect, which is partly mediated by a desire for environmental responsibility, highlights how social media can effectively promote sustainable habits and further sustainability objectives. Social media is still a powerful instrument for promoting sustainable practices and eco-conscious habits, even in the face of individual differences in beliefs and trust.	Zafar,et al. (2021). [49]
8	Effective social media marketing relies on high-quality, consumer-focused content that builds awareness, fosters business-customer relationships, and empowers consumers through easy information sharing. Maintaining a positive online reputation and cultivating strong client relationships are essential, as poor word-of-mouth can significantly damage a brand's image.	Varghese & Agrawal (2021). [50]
9	A major component of using social networks to sway consumer decisions is enjoyment, and Facebook-mediated marketing communication is a vital conduit for successful direct marketing campaigns.	Di Pietro & Pantano (2012). [51]
10	Consumer purchase behavior is strongly influenced by engagement, risk perception reduction, effective value communication, and social support. Businesses should foster a welcoming online environment to enhance customer involvement and encourage positive interactions, which in turn drive stronger purchase intentions.	Ebrahimi,et al. (2023). [52]

8] Digital Marketing in Ayurveda System A Study on Digital Marketing Strategies and SWOC Analysis of Himalaya

Strengths:

The company benefits from its strategic location at the foothills of the Himalayas, enhancing brand trust and customer perception. It leads the market with innovative frozen food offerings and maintains a strong inter-state distribution network to ensure timely availability of products. The use of resources and creative teams due to low production costs and automation have provided affordable products while maintaining coherent quality. Social networks, especially Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, stimulate high customer commitments and quick response time.

Weaknesses:

The company's reliance on seasonal raw materials and ongoing cash flow requirements are two major operational challenges that can result in production delays and higher expenses. The use of pesticides and preservatives raises manufacturing costs and may degrade the quality of the final product. Furthermore, the pressure to keep a competitive edge is increased by the growing competition from foreign businesses in the market for Ayurvedic products.

Opportunities:

Himalaya should take advantage of the rising demand for organic products to grow internationally. A solid marketing strategy is necessary for success in order to adjust to shifting consumer preferences and to properly position their products through increased promotional activities. While managing high product prices due

to raw material costs will be essential for maintaining competitiveness, concentrating on online business can help reach a wider customer base.

Threats:

The business must contend with issues like rising global demand for organic products, which could draw in new competitors, and rising raw material

costs brought on by significant cultivation investment. Products must have scientific validation in order to retain trust. The market is becoming more competitive as Ayurvedic products gain popularity. Furthermore, the company's dependence on agricultural raw materials exposes it to the risk of natural disasters, which could result in large losses.

Fig. 1: SWOC Analysis Framework

09] Marketing Strategy:

A business's marketing plan describes how it will satisfy customer needs and incorporates tactics for preserving ties with suppliers, employees, and shareholders.[53] In order to stay ahead of the competition in a market that is highly competitive, a company must be able to meet the needs of its customers more effectively than its competitors.[54] Strategy development and implementation are separated in the traditional marketing approach, which makes execution difficult.[55] Management has to carefully plan the marketing strategy because of the high expenses. To develop a customer-focused strategy that bolsters financial resources, marketing and finance must effectively communicate.[56] With the goal of evaluating a suitable strategic business plan, this approach assesses a firm's competitive position by matching its resources and expertise with environmental demands.[57] Understanding customer behavior, providing value to customers, and taking advantage of market competition are all crucial for gaining and preserving a competitive edge.[58]

10] Present Status of Herbal Medicine

Herbal medicine has gained popularity worldwide, with significant adoption even in developed countries. In France and Germany, about 70% of medical doctors regularly prescribe herbal remedies. Especially in the United States, the herbal market is growing rapidly, and FDA has relaxed the rules of herbal additives. In 1991, the EU's Chinese medicine market was estimated to be \$ 6 billion, and Germany, France and Italy were the lead. In 1996, the US market was worth \$4 billion, and it has probably doubled in size since then. The Indian herbal market is worth about \$1 billion, of which \$80 million comes from exports. Despite advances in pharmaceutical science, herbal medicine has survived and evolved: rigorous scientific analysis has demonstrated the effectiveness of herbal medicines and rejected unsupported claims. Many new drugs were obtained from natural sources, including antibacterial and antitumor treatment. Respect from traditional drugs such as penicillin (from Mold) and

Belladonna (used with ophthalmology and preservatives), and the value of plant sources in modern medicine I am.

11] Status of Herbal Medicine in India

Ayurveda medicine in India, based on 2,000 years of tradition, combines the scientific principles of ancient textbooks, such as the appeal of Atharvaveda, Samhita, Sushruta Samhita. Ayurveda, which means "knowledge of life," integrates diet and drug therapy, describes about 700 plantations in 50 categories, and solves the mental health problem. Plant parts such as bark, leaves and roots are often used in this treatment, which emphasizes the balance of rasa (taste), vipaka (post-digestive effect), virya (potency) and Prabhava (specific action).

Ayurvedic medicine plays

a particularly important role in liver protection, with around 170 botanical compounds from 110 different plants identified as having liver-protective properties. There are about 6,000 herbal formulas for liver health sold worldwide and 40 formulas are patented in India alone. The major herbal treatments for viral hepatitis include Silymarin from *Silibum marianum*, Kutaki (*Picrorrhiza kurroa*), *Phyllanthus* species (especially *P. niruri* and *P. amarus*), and glycyrrhizin-based preparations such as SNMC from Japan. Additionally, the Ayurvedic compound Liv 52 and various clinical trials involving herbs such as *Mucuna pruriens* for Parkinson's disease and *Phyllanthus amarus* for hepatitis have shown promising results in both animal and human studies. Most popular herbal brands are mentioned in figure no.1

Most popular herbal brands are mentioned in figure no.1.

12] Future prospects of herbal medicine market

About 75% of plant preparations worldwide have been inspired by traditional medicine, and they assess that 25% of modern drugs were born from plants used for the first time in traditional practices.

In India, around 70% of modern drugs are obtained from natural sources.

Medicinal plants are essential for therapeutic agents, semi-synthetic compounds and products in cosmetic and food industries. The growing acceptance of plant health care, especially in cosmetics, as well as the increase in health care costs, have stimulated demand.

As herbal products become more popular across the globe, demand is expected to rise in the coming years, with countries such as China and India, which are rich in medicinal plant species, becoming major suppliers.[59]

CONCLUSION

In the 20th century, scientific marketing played a key role in establishing Ayurveda as a globally recognised and scientifically validated healthcare system, and the introduction of modern technologies, including AI, has helped Ayurveda spread across the world. Its widespread acceptance has been fuelled by significant changes in philosophy, research, regulation and governance.

Reflections on postcolonialism and modernisation help contextualise the development of Ayurveda as a complementary and alternative medicine that integrates traditional wisdom and modern science, contributing to a more diverse global health system.

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